

Traditional Olive Groves and their Landscape: Agrotourism

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Centenary olive grove of the Lucio variety, located in Íllora, Granada.

Andalusia has unique landscapes and historic olive groves that not only produce high quality oil, but also have a great cultural and environmental heritage. The enhancement of these centuries-old olive groves through agrotourism is a strategic innovation in the revitalisation of the rural economy.

The centuries-old olive groves of the Montes Orientales de Granada are a symbol of cultural identity. The farm Finca Santa Catalina, located in the municipality of Íllora, has olive trees more than 200 years old, dating back to 1850. It is an agroforestry farm, grazed by cattle, where agrotourism is another key element in the management.

The property was acquired by the current owners because of their interest in preserving these natural monuments. Preservation and restoration tasks are being carried out here, including the construction of dykes to support the olive trees and contain run-off water. Archaeological work is also being carried out on the restoration of a mill and the dating of the olive grove.

This project enables the development of a connection with consumers through on-site experiences, such as guided tours, oil tastings, harvesting workshops and cultural events. Tourists are immersed in the production process, thus developing a stronger bond with the product and its origin. At the same time, this type of tourism promotes responsible practices, helping to mitigate rural depopulation and generating secondary employment.

Another of the advantages of using these olive groves for tourism is the diversification of income, which is complemented by the production of high quality and organic oils, specifically from the olives of these centenary olive trees. In fact, as a result, the Lucio 642 brand was born.

These visits are offered directly to groups or families, either through local travel agencies or through sustainable tourism platforms operating in the region. In this way, a change in the perception of olive oil as a landscape-generating element capable of maintaining cultural heritage is achieved.

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